

Newsletter No.1 April 2022

www.oxipro.eu

A research project funded under the EU H2020 programme, developing enzymes for environmental-friendly products

Welcome from the OXIPRO Project Coordinator, Dr. Gro Bjerga.

Over half of Europeans say that protecting the environment is very important, and 8 out of 10 are worried about [the impact of chemicals in everyday products](#), stating that we should 'change the way we produce and trade'.

[OXIPRO](#) is an EU-funded research project that rethinks the way we produce consumer goods by replacing hazardous chemicals and reducing water and energy demands by using enzyme technologies, in line with EU's plans to make goods more [environmentally-friendly and circular](#)

Your voice matters to OXIPRO.

We welcome you to collaborate with us to create change and shape OXIPRO's developments. [Register via our website](#) to stay up to date with our initiative and to take part in our events.

OXIPRO - the movie!

Through original visuals, our new video introduces the OXIPRO project and how it is contributing to the transition towards greener products, thereby enhancing the overall sustainability and competitiveness of the European bio-based economy strategy for a greener future.

[Watch the video](#)

Website upgrade for year two

As we approach the second year of our project, we've implemented a dynamic new project website. Feel free to explore it to find out about what we do, our partners, our innovative approach, synergies, the latest developments, and [how to get involved](#) in the OXIPRO community.

[Visit website](#)

Welcome to our Expert Advisors

The OXIPRO project is delighted to announce the establishment of an expert Advisory Board, whose advice and guidance, based on their specific fields of interest, will increase the value and contribute to the success of this initiative.

[Find out more](#)

OXIPRO Expert Advisory Board

Dr. Olav Lanes

Prof. Jennifer Littlechild

Dr. Karel De Winter

OXIPRO at OxiZymes 2022

OXIPRO is proud to announce that project partner Marco Fraaije, [Molecular Enzymology Group, University of Groningen](#) (image-right), has been invited as a speaker at the forthcoming [10th Edition of OxiZymes](#) meeting, to be hosted in Siena, Italy, from July 5-8, 2022.

[Find out more](#)

OXIPRO Synergies

OXIPRO is closely working with ongoing research initiatives, in particular with our sibling projects funded under the same topic:

- [EnXylaScope](#)
- [FuturEnzyme](#)
- [Radicalz](#)

Read about our first meeting [here](#).

Importantly, we are about to launch the first newsletter: 'The Active Site'. [Subscribe here](#) to receive first issue with news from all four projects, and find out more about our work.

OXIPRO's Sibling Projects

Forthcoming Events for your Calendar

- [International conference on Circular Economy and Green Growth](#)
- [Meetings and Webinars in 2022](#)
- [EU Green Week](#)
- [OECD Live Green Talks](#)
- [OxiZymes 2022](#)
- [Bioflavour 2022](#)

About OXIPRO

OXIPRO is a four-year initiative funded under the EU's Horizon 2020 programme and brings together a multidisciplinary team of researchers and stakeholders from 15 entities across Europe to focus on the development of novel enzymes for environment-friendly consumer products.

The OXIPRO partners are developing and deploying an efficient oxidoreductase foundry using cutting-edge bioinformatics and biotechnology, and by broadening the range of industrial oxidoreductases for more sustainable processes, this initiative will ultimately contribute to the transition to environment-friendly products, with detergents, textiles, sunscreens, and nutraceuticals.

Through the integration of computational workflows and state-of-the-art biotechnological technologies, OXIPRO will expedite the lab to market journey, while shortcutting downstream implementation and ensuring market uptake. This will be supported by ecosystem intelligence generated throughout the project as well as engagement with research, policy, societal and industrial actors in co-creation and interactions to maximise output and enable faster and systemic innovations.

For more information, contact:

Project Coordinator: [Dr. Gro Bjerga](#)

Communications: [Lesley Tobin](#)

To join the OXIPRO Community and receive project updates, [please register here](#)

hello@oxipro.eu

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